

Revisiting CO₂ Emissions and Global Warming: Implications for Society

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Abstract

This paper revisits the relationship between CO₂ emissions and global warming by analysing more than 70 million daily temperature observations from over 2000 weather stations across 51 countries, with records spanning from the pre-1900 era to 2024. Employing fixed effects models to isolate temperature trends from station-specific and seasonal variations, the study finds an overall warming trend of 0.0048°C [TAVG] per year, after controlling for urban built-up areas. The analysis reveals a significant disconnect between the rise in annual anthropogenic CO₂ emissions and the rate of temperature change. Notably, the period of the sharpest warming occurred in the early 20th century when CO₂ emission levels were modest. In contrast, subsequent periods with rapidly accelerating CO₂ emissions experienced slower warming or even cooling trends. These findings challenge the conventional assumption that human-induced CO₂ is the primary driver of global warming; they highlight key gaps in our understanding and necessitate not only a more critical approach across research, education, journalism, and organizational conduct, but also a thorough reassessment of the premise underlying current climate policies.

Keywords: Global warming; CO₂ emissions; Temperature trends; Climate change; Climate policy; AGW

JEL codes: Q54; Q56; Q58; C23

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1 Introduction

The premise that Carbon dioxide (CO₂) warms the planet is a foundational concept in modern climate science. An early influential study by Manabe and Wetherald (1967) estimated that a doubling of atmospheric CO₂ levels would lead to an approximate 2°C increase in atmospheric temperature, assuming constant relative humidity. Building upon this, a substantial body of contemporary research attributes the phenomenon of global warming primarily to human emissions of CO₂. For example, Matthews and Wynes, (2022) suggest that human-induced warming is likely to push global temperatures beyond the 1.5°C threshold in less than a decade. Other research treats this link as a foregone conclusion; Hönisch et al. (2025) synthesized 66 million years of paleo-CO₂ records, while Jones et al. (2023) take anthropogenic global warming (AGW) as a given to calculate national contributions from CO₂ and other greenhouse gases. Empirical studies, such as Stips et al. (2016), argue for a one-way causality from greenhouse gases to global mean surface temperature anomalies since 1850, identifying CO₂ as the main driver of recent warming. This perspective is central to policy discussions, with Kotz et al. (2024) highlighting how the financial burden of climate mitigation varies significantly based on emission trajectories. The reliance on this relationship is further noted by Sautner et al. (2023), who state, ”*Scientists have developed complex models that estimate the effect of greenhouse gas emissions on the global climate.*” The presumed impact of CO₂ extends to other climatic phenomena, with Iwakiri et al. (2025) finding that CO₂ mitigation could influence the frequency of El Niño events.

However, other climate studies highlight significant uncertainties and alternative explanations for observed warming, challenging the singular focus on CO₂. Hegerl et al. (2018) note that the most pronounced warming in the historical record - the Early Twentieth Century Warming (ETCW) - occurred when CO₂ emissions were still modest, and caution that the contribution of each causal factor remains uncertain. Looking at longer timescales, Schurer et al. (2013) find that changes in solar activity and major volcanic eruptions were the dominant influences on climate between 1400 and 1900, though they also identify a role for greenhouse gases in cooler periods. Examining more recent data, Lansner and Pepke Pedersen (2018) report a lack of warming in ocean air-sheltered temperature data after 1950. In a critical review for the US Department of Energy, Christy et al. (2025) argue that induced warming appears less economically damaging

than commonly believed and that aggressive mitigation strategies could be more harmful than beneficial. More fundamentally, some researchers propose entirely different primary drivers of warming. For instance, Nikolov and Zeller (2024) argue that warming trends are attributable to planetary albedo and solar irradiance variations, with no connection to CO₂.

Despite this ongoing debate, the idea of a near-total scientific consensus on AGW, often cited as 97% (Cook et al., 2013), has gained significant traction. However, the basis for this consensus claim raises several concerns. First, the finding that 3,896 papers endorsed AGW over a 21-year period (1991–2011) implies an average of one new paper on the topic every other day, which could suggest a herd mentality rather than a proliferation of independent evidence. If one strong piece of empirical evidence for AGW exists, such repetitive endorsement would be unnecessary. Second, it is unclear how many of these studies have made their data publicly available for independent scrutiny. This claim of consensus was nevertheless presented as "fact" and "not theories" in a US Congressional Hearing¹ in June 2013, attributed to NASA. The source provided therein as a reference, however, leads to an error page², raising further doubt about the veracity of the evidence underpinning the consensus. Despite these issues, the claim of 97% consensus maintains strong socio-political currency, as evidenced by its use in congressional hearings and its promotion by former US President Obama on Twitter one day after its publication.³

Against this backdrop of conflicting research and questions surrounding the proclaimed consensus, it is imperative to re-examine the raw evidence directly. This study aims to investigate whether global warming trends, as recorded by actual weather stations, can be primarily attributed to human emissions of CO₂. The analysis focuses specifically on anthropogenic CO₂ because policy interventions, including energy regulation, carbon pricing, and taxation, are designed to influence human-controlled emissions rather than natural carbon fluxes, which lie outside the scope of policy action. By employing a comprehensive dataset of publicly available daily temperature records spanning from the pre-1900 era to 2024, this paper uses econometric fixed-effects models to isolate temperature trends over various time windows. By comparing these empirically derived trends with

¹H.R. 2231, OFFSHORE ENERGY AND JOBS ACT PART 1 AND 2 | Congress.gov | Library of Congress

²<https://science.nasa.gov/climate/evidence> (accessed September 15 2024)

³Cook et al. paper was published on 15 May 2013; President Obama's tweet was posted on 16 May 2013.

the historical record of human CO₂ emissions, this analysis offers a transparent and visual assessment of the relationship, seeking to clarify the extent to which human-induced CO₂ is associated with the global warming phenomenon.

2 Data

The primary data source for this analysis is the Global Historical Climatology Network (GHCN) daily dataset ⁴, which was downloaded on 02 August 2025. This dataset provides weather information for various weather stations across the globe including station identifier, country name, date, minimum temperature, and maximum temperature. An average daily temperature is computed as the mean of the minimum and maximum daily temperature for each station.

Initial daily temperature records from all stations exceed 105 million observations. Seemingly erroneous observations are discarded. This includes temperature more than 57 °C or less than -90 °C; and observations where daily minimum temperatures are higher than the daily maximum temperatures for any stations. Discarding these erroneous observations drops available observations to 102 million records from 3094 stations. The dataset is further filtered to include only those stations with a continuous and extensive observational history, specifically those with records commencing on or before the year 1900 and extending to at least the year 2020. This selection criterion isolates a consistent cohort of stations, which is fundamental for minimizing biases that could arise from changes in the network of stations over time. We further drop observations for year 2025 as the year is not complete at the time of writing. After this cleaning process, the final sample for analysis has 42,456,992 records showing both minimum and maximum temperature from 992 weather stations across 29 countries. Alternatively, we relax the threshold of year 1900 to include weather stations where earliest temperature records are available from at least 1920 and this increases the sample to 66 million. Among these 992 stations, the vast majority are situated in the USA (840) followed by Germany (32), Russia (32), Sweden (16) and Canada (12), as shown in Figure 1.

The summary statistics for temperature is presented in Table 1. Data on annual human CO₂ emissions is from Our World In Data. Full list of number of

⁴ghcnd.all.tar.gz file downloaded from <https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/pub/data/ghcn/daily/>

Figure 1: Location of weather stations globally in the main sample

stations by country is provided in Appendix 1.

Table 1: Summary statistics of daily temperature. TAVG is the simple average of TMAX (maximum) and TMIN (minimum) temperature.

Statistic	Min Year 1900			Min Year 1920		
	TMAX	TMIN	TAVG	TMAX	TMIN	TAVG
No. of obs	42,456,992	42,456,992	42,456,992	66,389,666	66,389,666	66,389,666
Mean	17.09	4.73	10.91	16.97	4.39	10.68
Std. Dev.	12.19	10.96	11.27	12.33	11.07	11.38
Minimum	-63.40	-72.80	-64.65	-63.40	-72.80	-64.65
25th percentile	8.30	-2.20	3.25	8.30	-2.20	3.05
50th percentile	18.30	5.60	11.95	18.30	5.00	11.70
75th percentile	26.70	13.00	19.75	26.70	12.80	19.45
Maximum	53.50	44.40	44.70	56.10	44.40	44.70

2.1 Statistical Modelling of Temperature Trends

To quantify temperature trends, a panel fixed-effects regression model is employed. The model is specified to estimate the trend in a temperature variable as a function of time. We also control for seasonal cycles and level of urbanization later.

The basic regression is of the following form:

$$\text{Temperature}_{i,t} = f(\text{Time}_{i,t}) + \epsilon_{i,t} \quad (1)$$

where i indexes for individual weather station and t indexes for days.

The core of the regression isolates the underlying trend by including fixed effects for each station and for each month of the year. The station-level fixed effects absorb all unique, time-invariant attributes of a station, such as its specific geography, elevation, and local microclimate. This ensures that the model estimates the warming within each station over time, rather than being influenced by baseline temperature differences between stations.

We also control for earth’s orbital distance from the sun (seasonal trends) using dummy variables for each month. This inclusion of monthly fixed effects⁵ provides a seasonal adjustment, effectively removing the predictable annual temperature cycle from the data. This allows for a precise estimation of the long-term trend, independent of seasonal variability. To ensure the statistical validity of the results, the model assumes that the error terms are clustered at the station level and the standard errors are corrected accordingly by station (Petersen, 2009). As an alternative, to control for possible spatial dependence, standard errors are calculated by clustering the errors based on geographical proximity of stations. This is discussed in more detail in Section 4.1.

Temperature trends could be influenced by urban heat island (UHI) warming effects (Estrada and Perron, 2021; Spencer et al., 2025) since temperature in a given station could be influenced by urbanization over the years. To control for such UHI effects, we include the built-up percentage within a 10-km radius of the station.

Urban built-up area data were derived from the Global Human Settlement Layer (GHSL) GHS-BUILT-S R2023A dataset ⁶, obtained from the European Commission's Joint Research Centre. The data, provided at 100-meter spatial resolution, were processed for the years 1975 to 2024 at five-year intervals. For each weather station, built-up area statistics were extracted using zonal statistics within a circular buffer of 10 km radius. To ensure accurate surface area

⁵Including month fixed effects can be considered unnecessary in the context of this study. The distance to the sun (and the resulting seasons) is outside human control, and long-term temperature trends should be observable without controlling for seasonal variation. In this spirit and for transparency, we provide additional results in the appendices by excluding month dummies.

⁶https://jeodpp.jrc.ec.europa.eu/ftp/jrc-opendata/GHSL/GHS_BUILT_S_GLOBE_R2023A/

calculations across different latitudes, station coordinates were transformed from WGS84 (World Geodetic System 1984) to the World Mollweide equal-area projection before generating the buffers. The built-up percentage was calculated by summing the area of built-up pixels within each of the 10-km buffer and then dividing by the total buffer area. Since the data is available from 1975 onwards in five-year intervals, we control for urbanization only in the final time window of the regressions. This built-up data is available for all stations. Available data is projected to the next four years until new data becomes available. So in essence, urbanization level would be the same for each station for years 1975-1979; and the new built-up data from 1980 would remain the same until 1984, and so on.

The analysis is done iteratively on subsets of the data, focusing on the top stations as ranked by the number of available observations. Initially 100 stations with the highest number of observations are chosen. While 100 stations may offer a rich dataset with minimal missing values, it may also raise question about the generalizability of such trends owing to ‘small’ number of stations. To address this, we employ an iterative process for cohorts of 100, 200, and up to 1,000 top stations based on data availability. As the number of stations increases thereby allowing for a more generalizable sample, the missing values also increase. Hence, there is a trade-off in terms of choosing the number of stations. We also take an alternative approach of prioritizing stations based on the least level of missing data, as further discussed in section 4.2 later.

First, a full-period analysis is conducted by fitting a single regression model across the entire historical timeframe. The resulting trend lines for minimum, maximum, and average temperatures are plotted over a scatter plot of the raw daily temperature readings. This visualization offers a comprehensive overview of the long-term temperature trajectory.

Second, a multi-period analysis is performed to investigate potential changes in the rate of warming over time. The full historical period is partitioned into five, six, seven and 10 contiguous, equal-duration segments. A separate fixed-effects regression is independently fitted to the data within each of these segments. The resulting trend lines for each period are then plotted on a single chart, facilitating a direct visual comparison of the warming rates across different historical eras.

The annual human emission of CO₂ is then superimposed over warming trends over the same X-axis (year) but with a secondary Y-axis that displays global annual CO₂ emissions, allowing for a visual comparison between warming trends

and annual CO₂ output. So, though our initial approach to finding temperature trends relies on robust econometric techniques using fixed effects, the visualization approach is simpler for comparison purposes. Considering the predominantly two-dimensional nature of the data analysis - (specifically, warming over time and CO₂ emissions over time (assuming the absence of confounding factors such as seasonal trends and urbanization) - we initially rely on intuitive visualizations in two-dimensional planes. Subsequently, we tabulate cumulative temperature changes over specified time windows (e.g., 42 years or 35 years) alongside cumulative CO₂ emissions over the corresponding periods for comparative analysis.

3 Findings

For illustrative purposes, we start with 100 stations located across 12 countries with the highest number of observations available in the dataset and draw a single trendline over the entire duration of 1814 to 2024. The trendline for average global temperature (TAVG) is 0.0092 °C per year (p-value: 0.0000). As can be seen in Figure 2, the scatter plots prior to 1900 are dominated by warmer regions. More temperature data from other stations become available as year progresses. It is inconceivable that the temperature grew constantly over the entire duration but this gives an initial indication of the rise in global temperatures over the years.

To investigate potential changes in the rate of warming over time, we now use the same 100 stations but subdivide the overall duration of 210 years into multiple contiguous timeframes of 21 years (10 equal periods), 30 years (7 equal periods), 35 years (6 equal periods) and 42 years (5 equal periods).

To simplify our discussion, we first consider five contiguous, equal-duration segments of 42 years each, as shown in Figure 3. Annual CO₂ emissions are also plotted on the chart, highlighting a clear discontinuity in trendlines across distinct time periods. The number of observations starts being comparable starting from 1899, with all the three time-windows after that point having more than 1.4 million observations each. This also signifies that the missing data is less than 2.5% for the weather stations during the last three time periods.⁷ Interestingly, the highest rate of increase in temperature can be observed during the most recent 1983-2024 period at the rate of 0.0239 °C per year for TAVG (average temperature), after

⁷The number of observations for 1899-1940 is 1,498,715 against maximum possible daily observations of approximately 1,533,000 (=100*42*365), registering a data availability of 97.8%.

Figure 2: Global temperature trendline based on 100 weather stations

controlling for seasonal variations and UHI. Without controlling for UHI, trend for this latest period is higher at 0.0293 °C per year.

The second highest rate of increase was during 1899-1940 (0.0169 per year). This is higher than the rate of warming during 1941 -1982 when a cooling trend of -0.0065 per year is observed. A visual inspection shows that CO₂ emission was relatively low during 1899-1940 whereas it has steadily increased during the subsequent periods (Figure 3). Comparative CO₂ emissions and rate of rise during each of the 42-year time frames are presented in Table 2. It can be noted that cumulative CO₂ emissions during the cooling period of 1941-1982 (459.2 billion tons) was 3.3 times more than that during 1899-1940 (139.7 billion tons). This is counterintuitive to the idea that CO₂ is the main driver of global warming, at least during 1941-1982.

For the other timeframes of 35 years, 30 years and 21 years, we present the summary statistics in tables below in turn. In all of the tables Table 3, Table 4, and Table 5, there are instances of temperature rise being higher during a given time frame despite the CO₂ emissions being a fraction of later time frames when temperature rise was slower. For instance, during 1905-1934 in Table 4, the temperature rose by 0.0238 (CO₂ emission: 101.1) compared to slower rise

Figure 3: Global temperature trendlines based on 100 weather stations across 5 equal time periods

in temperature during 1965-1994 (0.0236) despite the CO2 emission being more than five times higher (549.9).

We now focus on 500 weather stations for better generalization (Figure 4). These weather stations offer a compromise in that they cover more than half of the weather stations available in our final sample (of 992) and have highest number of daily observations available. The overall warming trend for the entire duration stands at 0.0052 C per year (p-value: 0.0000) which is substantially lower than what was observed with just 100 stations (0.0092 C per year).

Though we have increased the number of stations, the number of missing values also increases. Against the possible number of observations of approximately 7.66 million ($=500 \times 42 \times 365$), the observations in the last three periods (Figure 5) are all in excess of 7.33 million, which shows that less than 4.4% of observations are missing.

The breakdown of entire duration into five contiguous equal-duration segments of 42 years each reveals further insights into how temperatures evolved over the years. Among the last three time-windows with highest number of observations (more than 7.3 million in each), the time period of 1899-1940 witnessed the

Table 2: Temperature trend and cumulative CO2 emission over 42-year time frames based on 100 weather stations with highest number of daily observations

42-Year Period	Number of Obs	Temp change per year (°C)	p-value	Cum. CO2 emission (Billion Tons)
1815-1856	46,158	-0.010	0.323	4.9
1857-1898	545,151	0.008	0.150	35.1
1899-1940	1,498,715	0.017	0.000	139.7
1941-1982	1,514,517	-0.0065	0.000	459.2
1983-2024	1,499,529	0.024	0.000	1208.9

Table 3: Temperature trend and cumulative CO2 emission over 35-year time frames based on 100 weather stations with highest number of daily observations

35-Year Period	Number of Obs	Temp change per year (°C)	p-value	Cum. CO2 emission (Billion Tons)
1815-1849	32,701	-0.0081	0.500	3.3
1850-1884	180,194	0.0004	0.963	18.0
1885-1919	1,124,691	0.0080	0.000	77.6
1920-1954	1,253,462	0.0048	0.015	158.0
1955-1989	1,266,832	0.0083	0.000	526.2
1990-2024	1,246,190	0.0246	0.000	1064.8

sharpest rate of rise in global temperature (0.0213 C per year; p-value: 0.0000), which is higher than the rate in the most recent period of 1983-2024 (0.016 per year for TAVG, after controlling for UHI). The temperature trend during this recent period without controlling for UHI is 0.0205 C per year, which is still lower than that during 1899-1940.

More detailed summary information along with cumulative CO2 emissions during each of the time frames are presented in Table 6. It can be observed that 1899-1940 witnessed the sharpest rise in temperature with cumulative CO2 emissions of 139.7 billion tons whereas subsequent time frames register a slower rate of rising and even cooling despite having CO2 emissions higher by 3.3 times and 8.6 times during 1941-1982 (cooling -0.0143 per year) and 1983-2024 (0.0168 per year) respectively.

Cumulative CO2 emissions and accumulated temperature based on statistically significant trends for each of the 42-year timeframe are depicted in Figure 6.

For the other timeframes of 35 years, 30 years and 21 years, the summary statistics based on 500 weather stations are presented in tables below in turn.

Figure 4: Global temperature trendline based on 500 weather stations

Figure 5: Global temperature trendlines based on 500 weather stations across 5 equal time periods

Table 4: Temperature trend and cumulative CO2 emission over 30-year time frames based on 100 weather stations with highest number of daily observations

30-Year Period	Number of Obs	Temp change per year (°C)	p-value	Cum. CO2 emission (Billion Tons)
1815-1844	23,625	-0.0185	0.188	2.4
1845-1874	84,925	0.0049	0.592	10.6
1875-1904	696,607	0.0131	0.000	39.5
1905-1934	1,066,804	0.0238	0.000	101.1
1935-1964	1,080,967	-0.0102	0.000	193.7
1965-1994	1,086,336	0.0236	0.000	549.9
1995-2024	1,064,806	0.0333	0.000	950.6

Table 5: Temperature trend and cumulative CO2 emission over 21-year time frames based on 100 weather stations with highest number of daily observations

21-Year Period	Number of Obs	Temp change per year (°C)	p-value	Cum. CO2 emission (Billion Tons)
1815-1835	12,919	0.0484	0.000	1.4
1836-1856	33,239	0.0092	0.393	3.5
1857-1877	82,025	0.0033	0.802	10.2
1878-1898	463,126	0.0254	0.000	24.9
1899-1919	746,277	-0.0036	0.078	58.9
1920-1940	752,438	0.0127	0.000	80.9
1941-1961	754,886	-0.0041	0.235	136.8
1962-1982	759,631	0.0113	0.000	322.4
1983-2003	759,086	0.0321	0.000	484.7
2004-2024	740,443	0.0416	0.000	724.2

In each of the tables, instances of higher warming trend can be seen in earlier periods with moderate levels of CO2 emissions. For instance, the duration 1885-1919 (Table 7), 1905-1934 (Table 8), 1878-1898 (Table 9) exhibit higher rise than some or all of the subsequent periods with much higher CO2 emissions.

It is noted that the p-values (>0.1) in some cases do not denote statistical significance during recent periods, especially when the time frame is divided in six equal periods and 10 equal periods. The 35-year period during 1955-1989 especially stands out in Table 7.

For brevity, we provide only one figure (for 10 periods of 21 years each) to depict cumulative CO2 emissions and temperature change based on 500 weather stations in Figure 7.

Figure 6: Cumulative CO₂ emissions and cumulative temperature changes based on 500 weather stations across 5 equal time periods of 42 years (only statistically significant temperature trends are shown)

Figure 7: Cumulative CO₂ emissions and cumulative temperature changes based on 500 weather stations across 10 equal time periods of 21 years (only statistically significant temperature trends are shown)

Table 6: Temperature trend and cumulative CO2 emission over 42-year time frames based on 500 weather stations with highest number of daily observations

42-Year Period	Number of Obs	Temp change per year (°C)	p-value	Cum. CO2 emission (Billion Tons)
1815-1856	46,786	-0.0096	0.325	4.9
1857-1898	1,205,454	0.0132	0.031	35.1
1899-1940	7,335,273	0.0213	0.000	139.7
1941-1982	7,503,059	-0.0143	0.000	459.2
1983-2024	7,388,781	0.0168	0.000	1208.9

Table 7: : Temperature trend and cumulative CO2 emission over 35-year time frames based on 500 weather stations with highest number of daily observations

35-Year Period	Number of Obs	Temp change per year (°C)	p-value	Cum. CO2 emission (Billion Tons)
1815-1849	32,701	-0.0081	0.500	3.3
1850-1884	206,326	0.0022	0.762	18.0
1885-1919	4,628,354	0.0041	0.000	77.6
1920-1954	6,195,520	0.0029	0.131	158.0
1955-1989	6,276,268	0.0005	0.790	526.2
1990-2024	6,140,184	0.0190	0.000	1064.8

We now examine the full set of weather stations available in the final sample. There are 992 stations across 29 countries. The proportion of missing observations also increases due to this. For example, out of possible 15.2 million observations in each period, 13.94 million observations are available during the most recent period denoting a loss of data of approximately 9.2%.

The overall trend of warming stands at (0.0054 °C TAVG per year; p-value: 0.0000) (Figure 8), which is similar to the earlier finding based on 500 stations. For comparison, we provide a similar chart, but without adjustment for seasonal variation, Appendix 2. As we divide the years into five contiguous equal-duration segments of 42 years each, the overall message remains qualitatively similar.

Earlier time window (1899-1940) registered the sharpest rate of rise in global temperature (0.0213 °C per year; p-value: 0.0000) despite annual CO2 emissions (139.7 bl tons) being at modest levels Figure 9 and Table 10, whereas later periods corresponding to sharp increase in CO2 emissions show lower rate of rise (0.0167 °C per year during 1983-2024, after allowing for UHI⁸; p-value: 0.0000) or

⁸The temperature trend without allowing for UHI for the final period 1983-2024 stands at

Table 8: Temperature trend and cumulative CO2 emission over 30-year time frames based on 500 weather stations with highest number of daily observations

30-Year Period	Number of Obs	Temp change per year (°C)	p-value	Cum. CO2 emission (Billion Tons)
1815-1844	23,625	-0.0185	0.188	2.4
1845-1874	94,344	0.0066	0.471	10.6
1875-1904	2,139,076	0.0029	0.560	39.5
1905-1934	5,253,327	0.0298	0.000	101.1
1935-1964	5,349,448	-0.0128	0.000	193.7
1965-1994	5,369,078	0.0163	0.000	549.9
1995-2024	5,250,455	0.0242	0.000	950.6

Table 9: : Temperature trend and cumulative CO2 emission over 21-year time frames based on 500 weather stations with highest number of daily observations

21-Year Period	Number of Obs	Temp change per year (°C)	p-value	Cum. CO2 emission (Billion Tons)
1815-1835	12,919	0.0484	0.000	1.4
1836-1856	33,867	0.0094	0.383	3.5
1857-1877	93,437	0.0036	0.765	10.2
1878-1898	1,112,017	0.0316	0.000	24.9
1899-1919	3,615,141	0.0000	0.990	58.9
1920-1940	3,720,132	0.0168	0.000	80.9
1941-1961	3,732,304	-0.0136	0.001	136.8
1962-1982	3,770,755	-0.0007	0.812	322.4
1983-2003	3,744,617	0.0203	0.000	484.7
2004-2024	3,644,164	0.0322	0.000	724.2

even cooling ((-0.0133 °C per year during 1941-1982; p-value: 0.0000) in global temperatures (Table 10). A similar chart using raw temperature without seasonal adjustment is presented in Appendix 3 .

The cumulative CO2 emissions and temperature change based on all 992 weather stations over five equal timeframes of 42 years are shown in Table 10 and Figure 10. The cumulative emissions and cumulative temperature depiction for 10 periods of 21 years each is relegated to Appendix 4.

0.0209 °C per year.

Figure 8: Global temperature trendline based on all available (992) weather stations

Figure 9: Global temperature trendlines based on all (992) weather stations across 5 equal time periods

Table 10: Temperature trend and cumulative CO2 emission over 42-year time frames based on all available (992) weather stations in the final sample

42-Year Period	Number of Obs	Temp change per year (°C)	p-value	Cum. CO2 emission (Billion Tons)
1815-1856	46,786	-0.0096	0.325	4.9
1857-1898	1,725,382	0.0126	0.007	35.1
1899-1940	12,542,904	0.0213	0.000	139.7
1941-1982	14,197,820	-0.0133	0.000	459.2
1983-2024	13,944,100	0.0167	0.000	1208.9

4 Robustness Checks

4.1 Alternative standard errors

As an alternative to correcting for possible spatial dependence, we implement two-way clustered standard errors, correcting for both station-level autocorrelation and spatial dependence across stations based on geographical clusters. Geographic clusters are created using K-Means clustering⁹ on station coordinates and we arbitrarily create 50 such clusters, as depicted in Figure 11. Results (available on request) do not alter the statistical significance of the findings so far.

4.2 Selecting weather station based on least missing data

We re-run the regression models by prioritising weather stations with the least missing data. A weather station with records starting in 1816 could have more observations than a weather station with records starting in 1900, despite the latter having higher annual observation density. Hence, instead of taking into account the number of observations for each station, we prioritise stations having missing data of no more than 5%. The overall results remain qualitatively similar. Results are not shown for brevity but are available on request from the author.

4.3 Selecting additional weather stations

We relax our selection criteria to include stations where data is available from at least 1920 (relaxed from 1900 from baseline results). This still allows for examining

⁹Clusters are created using KMeans package from <https://scikit-learn.org> . Random state of 42 is used to ensure replicability.

Figure 10: Cumulative CO₂ emissions and cumulative temperature changes based on 992 weather stations across 5 equal time periods of 42 years (only statistically significant temperature trends are shown)

Figure 11: Geographical clusters for full sample of weather stations

stations with at least 100 years of daily recorded temperature and increases the number of weather stations in the sample to 1622 from 40 countries. The number of observations also increases to 66.39 million but overall trends and results remain qualitatively similar to earlier findings. The temperature (TAVG) trend based on this expanded set of stations for the overall period stands at 0.006 C per year (p-value 0.0000 based on 50 geographical clusters) [see Appendix 5] and the periodic trends are also qualitatively similar to previous findings (Figure 12).

We further relax selection criteria to include stations where data is available from at least 1970. Though this leads to selecting stations with less than 60 years of temperature data history, this nevertheless enhances representation to 51 countries [see Appendix 6] and increases overall observations of 76.6 million from 2038 weather stations. The results remain qualitatively similar and shown in Appendix 7.

Table 11: Temperature trend and cumulative CO2 emission over 42-year time frames based on expanded set of 1622 weather stations

42-Year Period	Number of Obs	Temp change per year (°C)	p-value	SE cluster by	Cum. CO2 emission (Billion Tons)
1815-1856	46,786	-0.0096	0.325	Station	4.9
1857-1898	1,725,382	0.0126	0.040	Geographic	35.1
1899-1940	18,656,120	0.0221	0.000	Geographic	139.7
1941-1982	23,199,221	-0.0106	0.000	Geographic	459.2
1983-2024	22,762,157	0.0182	0.000	Geographic	1,208.9

Table 12: Temperature trend and cumulative CO2 emission over 35-year time frames based on expanded set of 1662 weather

35-Year Period	Number of Obs	Temp change per year (°C)	p-value	SE cluster by	Cum. CO2 emission (Billion Tons)
1815-1849	32,701	-0.0081	0.500	Station	3.3
1850-1884	246,249	0.0032	0.680	Geographic	18.0
1885-1919	9,488,998	0.0009	0.648	Geographic	77.6
1920-1954	18,146,505	0.0046	0.006	Geographic	158.0
1955-1989	19,627,963	0.0018	0.324	Geographic	526.2
1990-2024	18,847,250	0.0189	0.000	Geographic	1,064.8

The statistical significance gets affected in a number of time-frames when the error terms are assumed to be clustered around geographical clusters. Tables showing trends over various time windows, along with the statistical significance,

Table 13: Temperature trend and cumulative CO2 emission over 30-year time frames based on expanded set of 1662 weather stations

35-Year Period	Number of Obs	Temp change per year (°C)	p-value	SE cluster by	Cum. CO2 emission (Billion Tons)
1815-1844	23,625	-0.0185	0.188	Station	2.4
1845-1874	108,705	0.0060	0.501	Geographic	10.6
1875-1904	3,401,262	-0.0018	0.753	Geographic	39.5
1905-1934	13,701,738	0.0291	0.000	Geographic	101.0
1935-1964	16,288,173	-0.0094	0.000	Geographic	193.7
1965-1994	16,807,653	0.0171	0.000	Geographic	549.9
1995-2024	16,058,510	0.0216	0.000	Geographic	950.6

for this expanded set of stations are presented in Table 11, Table 12, Table 13 and Table 14.

Table 14: Temperature trend and cumulative CO2 emission over 21-year time frames based on expanded set of 1662 weather stations

35-Year Period	Number of Obs	Temp change per year (°C)	p-value	SE cluster by	Cum. CO2 emission (Billion Tons)
1815-1835	12,919	0.0484	0.000	Station	1.4
1836-1856	33,867	0.0094	0.383	Station	3.5
1857-1877	111,981	0.0088	0.473	Geographic	10.2
1878-1898	1,613,401	0.0300	0.000	Geographic	24.9
1899-1919	7,995,780	-0.0030	0.299	Geographic	58.9
1920-1940	10,660,340	0.0223	0.000	Geographic	80.9
1941-1961	11,401,160	-0.0075	0.067	Geographic	136.8
1962-1982	11,798,061	-0.0010	0.759	Geographic	322.4
1983-2003	11,702,110	0.0256	0.000	Geographic	484.7
2004-2024	11,060,047	0.0283	0.000	Geographic	724.2

4.4 Examining rolling time periods

So far, we have examined pre-determined, fixed, contiguous time periods to observe possible warming or cooling trends. However, such trends may manifest over different time windows than those explored. To account for this, we analyse temperature trends over rolling 30-year, 40-year, and 50-year periods. For each rolling window, we repeat the station-fixed regressions with monthly dummy variables (but without the urban built-up control), using standard errors that allow for possible spatial correlation. Statistically significant results for the 40-year

Figure 12: Cumulative CO₂ emissions and cumulative temperature changes based on expanded set of 1622 weather stations across 10 equal time periods of 21 years (only statistically significant temperature trends are considered)

windows are shown in Figure 13. The cumulative temperature rise remains high during mid-period windows (approximately 1895–1934 to 1905–1944) despite modest CO₂ emissions during the corresponding years. Similar additional graphs (not shown for brevity) are produced for the 30-year and 50-year windows, using both 5% and 10% missing-data thresholds and additionally restricting to stations with the highest number of observations. The overall findings are qualitatively similar.

4.5 Allowing for cooling counter-effects of aerosol

Aerosols are theoretically expected to lower surface temperatures (Wild, 2009), potentially to a significant extent (Andreae et al., 2005). Specifically, sulfate aerosols are expected to primarily affect climate by scattering incoming solar radiation, ultimately exerting a cooling influence (Charlson et al., 1992). To account for this, we control for anthropogenic aerosol loading using sulfate aerosol extinction optical depth (SUEXTTAU) from MERRA-2 satellite data¹⁰. We process this data by converting UTC timestamps to local solar time (LST) and calculating a weighted average concentration during peak daylight hours (11 am to 5 pm). This

¹⁰<https://goldsmr4.gesdisc.eosdis.nasa.gov/data/MERRA2>

Figure 13: Cumulative temperature change and CO₂ emissions over 40-year rolling periods based on stations with least missing data (only statistically significant temperature trends are considered)

window is chosen because sulphate-induced dimming, if present, would be most likely to influence the daily maximum temperature (TMAX), which typically occurs during these hours. This metric is derived using inverse distance weighting from the four nearest MERRA-2 grid cells to each weather station.

Since reliable satellite aerosol data¹¹ is available only from 1980 onwards, we include this control only in the final period of our analysis. We retain all other model specifications (including seasonal variations and station fixed effects) and re-estimate the regression for maximum daily temperature. The results [shown in Appendix 8 (992 stations) and Appendix 9 (1662 stations)] do exhibit statistically significant negative association between sulfate concentrations and daily maximum temperature, but the impact is marginal with little or no change to the temperature slope. This suggests that anthropogenic sulfate loading has not significantly masked the temperature rise in recent periods in our sample.

¹¹We focus on sulfate aerosols rather than other anthropogenic aerosol for two main reasons. First, sulfates constitute the dominant anthropogenic cooling agent (Charlson et al., 1992). Second, the climate impact of black carbon on surface temperature remains highly uncertain and complex (Sand et al., 2020).

5 Concluding Remarks and Limitations

Interdisciplinary research has moved beyond simply acknowledging global warming to exploring the complex interplay between environmental challenges and societal outcomes. Studies in academic journals reveal how CO₂ emissions influence firm performance, investor behaviour, disclosure practices, and broader economic costs. Key research themes include the pricing of carbon risk in financial markets, the role of corporate disclosure in reducing emissions, and methods for measuring and hedging climate-related exposures. This body of work consistently highlights the negative environmental and societal consequences linked to increased CO₂ emissions.

However, a direct examination of publicly available daily temperature data from weather stations does not align with the notion that CO₂ is the primary driver of global warming. If this were the case, periods with higher CO₂ emissions would exhibit a faster rate of warming than periods with lower emissions. In contrast, this study finds that some recent periods have witnessed global cooling despite sharp increases in CO₂ emissions. Furthermore, the long-term temperature rise was steeper in earlier periods when CO₂ emissions were modest compared to current levels. These results hold despite changes in how time periods are defined (fixed versus rolling windows) and how weather stations are selected (based on number of observations or missing-data thresholds).

The evidence presented herein raises serious questions about the established assumption regarding the impact of CO₂ emissions on global warming. While Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) (2023, p. 42) states that “*Human activities, principally through emissions of greenhouse gases, have unequivocally caused global warming...*”, the empirical evidence presented herein does not provide support to such straightforward relationship.

5.1 Implications for academia

Given these findings, academic research should approach the concept of anthropogenic global warming (AGW) or (man-made) climate change with a degree of caution. Rather than treating AGW as a foregone conclusion, scholars in all fields should be encouraged to acknowledge the existing uncertainties. When building models or theories that treat CO₂ as the primary driver of warming, it would be prudent to include a caveat noting that the empirical evidence for this direct link

is still a subject of debate.

This call for critical appraisal extends to education. Educational materials, particularly for school children, should present the topic of global warming or climate change with more nuance. Instead of teaching AGW as an absolute and settled truth, curricula should aim to provide a more balanced perspective that includes the scientific method's reliance on questioning and verification. Fostering an environment of critical inquiry will better equip students to understand the complexities of climate science.

5.2 Implications for policymakers

The findings presented in this paper have significant and actionable implications for policymakers. A tremendous amount of effort and resources have been expended towards containing CO₂ emissions, with the explicit assumption that CO₂ drives global warming. As this premise now warrants closer scrutiny, a comprehensive review of all climate policies built upon this foundation is essential to ensure that such policies are effective, economically sound, and based on robust empirical evidence.

5.3 Implications for private and public organizations

Private and public organizations have increasingly institutionalized voluntary carbon reduction measures, such as the Science Based Targets initiative (SBTi) and the Voluntary Carbon Market (VCM), under the assumption that these efforts are critical for climate stability (Kreibich and Hermwille, 2021; Tilsted et al., 2023). However, if the causal link between anthropogenic CO₂ and warming is weak or non-existent, as this research suggests, these costly initiatives may represent a significant misallocation of capital. Private firms have a duty, within the bounds of law, to act in the best interest of the shareholders. Hence, a rational realignment of corporate sustainability would therefore pivot away from carbon-centric metrics toward adaptation strategies and genuine resource efficiency, which offer measurable economic returns independent of such carbon metrics.

5.4 Implications for media

Media outlets have actively positioned themselves as enforcers of informal environmental regulation, using carbon news coverage to pressure the private sector into compliance (Ye and Qi, 2025). The media's role in amplifying the narrative of catastrophic anthropogenic warming warrants critical re-examination in light of the evidence challenging the purported anthropogenic CO₂-temperature nexus. The results of this study suggest that this media-driven narrative is disconnected from the observational record. A responsible media approach would therefore prioritize a more balanced presentation of findings grounded in auditable and verifiable empirical evidence.

5.5 Limitations

This study has its limitations. One of the concerns relates to the quality of data. It is known that raw temperature data from some weather stations are not digitized properly. For example, UK weather stations in Armagh, Oxford, Sheffield, Durham and Stornoway are some of the longest-running stations. Upon a Freedom of Information request (by the author) for raw daily temperature data from these stations, the Met Office UK in their letter dated 27 March 2025 stated that *"Data that has not been through the QC processes (Version 0' values) remain undigitized and are only available in paper form prior to 1960 so we have not been able to provide that dataset."* This can raise issues about the quality of the reconstructed data when raw data itself remains undigitized. Similarly, given that the data goes through a quality control process, the possibility of noise being introduced in such reconstructed data remains. Future research would benefit from a systematic effort to digitize these historical archives, which would enable a more robust and direct analysis.

Second, stations are mainly land-based and concentrated in the US and Europe, with very sparse representation especially from Africa, South America, and Southeast Asia, even in the expanded sample. This can raise questions about whether the warming and cooling trends observed in this study apply to these under-represented areas. Collection of long-term, high-quality temperature data from across the globe is essential to support future research.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Number of weather stations by country

Country	Number of stations	Country	Number of stations
United States	840	Sri Lanka	2
Germany	32	Belgium	1
Russia	32	Ireland	1
Sweden	16	Slovenia	1
Canada	12	Greenland [Dk]	1
Australia	9	Uzbekistan	1
United Kingdom	7	France	1
Austria	6	Lithuania	1
Ukraine	5	Georgia	1
Romania	4	Belarus	1
Croatia	4	Moldova	1
Kazakhstan	3	Azerbaijan	1
Puerto Rico [US]	3	Algeria	1
Turkmenistan	2	Senegal	1
Switzerland	2		

Appendix 2: Global temperature trendline based on raw temperature data not adjusted for seasonal variations – top 1000 stations by observations

Appendix 3: Global temperature trendlines based on raw temperature data not adjusted for seasonal variations over 5 time periods – top 1000 stations by observations

Appendix 4: Cumulative CO2 emissions and cumulative temperature changes based on 992 weather stations across 10 equal time periods of 21 years (only statistically significant temperature trends are shown)

Appendix 5: Global temperature trendline based on expanded set of weather stations

Appendix 6: Expanded set of weather stations with data available from at least 1970

Appendix 7: Global temperature trendlines adjusted for seasonal variations over 5 time periods – top 2100 stations by observation

Appendix 8: TMAX and sulphate aerosol (992 stations)

Period	Change /year (°C)	Obs	p- value	Urban Coeff	Su Coeff	SU p-value	Duration
1983-2024	0.0116	13,944,100	0.000	0.14	-1.85	0.054	42
1990-2024	0.0162	11,548,111	0.000	0.113	-1.42	0.127	35
1995-2024	0.0235	9,841,909	0.000	0.151	-0.22	0.847	30
1983-2003	0.0097	7,162,352	0.063	nan	-2.66	0.010	21
2004-2024	0.0301	6,781,748	0.000	0.387	0.47	0.707	21

Appendix 9: TMAX and sulphate aerosol (1622 stations)

Period	Change /year (°C)	Obs	p- value	Urban Coeff	Su Coeff	SU p-value	Duration
1983-2024	0.0121	22,762,157	0.000	0.122	-2.36	0.039	42
1990-2024	0.0157	18,847,250	0.000	0.107	-1.95	0.080	35
1995-2024	0.0226	16,058,510	0.000	0.143	-0.92	0.520	30
1983-2003	0.0109	11,702,110	0.034	nan	-3.08	0.003	21
2004-2024	0.0297	11,060,047	0.000	0.346	-0.43	0.767	21